

Identification of potential anti-onchocercal compounds from *Annona muricata* using molecular docking and dynamics simulations

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Onchocerciasis
Glutathione-S-transferase
Annona muricata
Molecular docking
Molecular dynamics simulation

ABSTRACT

Onchocerciasis is a neglected tropical disease caused by *Onchocerca volvulus*. It affects approximately 37 million people globally, with 99 % of cases concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa. Notably, it leads to an estimated 1.8 million cases of visual impairment and 270,000 cases of blindness annually. *O. volvulus* glutathione-S-transferases (Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2) have been identified as potential drug targets due to their critical role in parasite survival. Consequently, this study employs molecular modeling techniques to identify potential inhibitors of these proteins from *Annona muricata* compounds. To begin with, a total of 198 compounds were retrieved from *A. muricata* and screened via molecular docking to predict their binding affinities for Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2. Subsequently, the promising candidates underwent binding free energy calculations, followed by assessments of drug-likeness, pharmacokinetics, and toxicity. Molecular dynamics simulations were then conducted to evaluate the stability of selected compounds within the active sites of the targets. The results identified several *A. muricata* compounds with high predicted binding affinities for both targets, with galactomannan exhibiting the highest docking scores (-7.764 and -10.021 kcal/mol) compared to ivermectin (-3.159 and -5.166 kcal/mol). Further evaluation highlighted caffeic acid, among the hit compounds, as a promising candidate due to its favorable drug-like properties, pharmacokinetics, and toxicity profile. Furthermore, molecular dynamics simulations confirmed the stable interactions of this compound with both protein targets. In conclusion, this study identifies caffeic acid as a potential dual inhibitor of Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2. However, further experimental validation is required to confirm its therapeutic potential.

1. Introduction

Onchocerciasis, commonly known as river blindness, is a neglected tropical disease caused by the filarial nematode *Onchocerca volvulus*. The disease affects approximately 37 million people worldwide, with 99 % of cases concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa, leading to an estimated 1.8 million cases of visual impairment and 270,000 cases of blindness annually [34]. *O. volvulus* larvae are transmitted to the human host via the bites of blackflies (*Simulium* spp.), after which larvae mature into adult worms capable of producing millions of microfilariae, which migrate through the skin, causing severe itching, skin discoloration, and ocular damage [9,10].

Upon human infection, a key survival strategy employed by

parasites, including *O. volvulus*, is their reliance on the activity of glutathione-S-transferases (GSTs). These enzymes play a crucial role in transforming toxic endogenous and exogenous compounds into non-toxic substances through conjugation with reduced glutathione, thereby protecting the parasite from harmful reactive species produced by the host's immune system [23]. Additionally, GSTs are involved in modulating the host's immune response, facilitating drug resistance, and regulating oxidative stress, which are critical for the parasite's survival and persistence within the host [23,28]. It is worth noting that three distinct GSTs have been identified in *O. volvulus*: Ov-GST1 is a prostaglandin D synthase that participates in the production of parasite-derived prostanoids, which functions in restraining the host's effector responses, further enhancing the parasite's ability to evade the

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.insilico.2025.100085>

Received 21 May 2025; Received in revised form 22 August 2025; Accepted 7 October 2025

Available online 10 October 2025

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immune system [17,30]. Conversely, Ov-GST2 neutralizes toxic products that result from the immune-mediated damage to the parasite's membranes. Also, Ov-GST3 plays a protective role against intracellular and environmental reactive oxygen species, with its expression localized to the eggshell during the morula stage of embryo formation [17,28]. In the development of newer treatment modalities against *O. volvulus*, Ov-GST1, and Ov-GST2 are considered more viable candidates for therapeutic interventions due to their broader functional roles and consistent expression throughout the lifecycle of *O. volvulus* as opposed to the expression of Ov-GST3 [28]. Moreover, Ov-GST2 exhibits significant differences in sequence and structure relative to the human counterpart [24]. Hence, Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 are considered viable targets for drug discovery.

The treatment of onchocerciasis is largely based on the use of ivermectin, which targets the microfilariae, the juvenile form of the parasite. However, ivermectin is ineffective against adult worms, or macrofilariae, necessitating repeated treatments over a prolonged period (10–15 years) to manage the infection effectively [6]. Moreover, the drug's efficacy is hindered by the emergence of resistance, particularly in regions with long-standing mass drug administration programs [22], which complicates control efforts. An additional challenge arises when individuals are co-infected with loa, as ivermectin is contraindicated in such cases due to the risk of severe adverse reactions like encephalopathy [9]. Despite these limitations, the development of new therapeutic options is hindered by the absence of drugs capable of targeting adult worms effectively, hence necessitating the need for novel treatments that can address both juvenile and adult stages of the parasite.

In the search for alternative treatment modalities for onchocerciasis, medicinal plants are explored as viable sources due to the plethora of bioactive compounds with numerous pharmacological properties they possess [17]. Among these, *Annona muricata* (soursop) stands out due to its rich array of bioactive molecules that exhibit various therapeutic effects. Historically, *Annona muricata* has been used in traditional medicine to treat conditions such as fever, diabetes, and infections caused by bacteria, fungi, and parasites [18]. Ethnobotanical studies have further highlighted the plant's anthelmintic, anti-hypertensive, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties [19]. Despite this broad medicinal applications of *Annona muricata*, no research has focused on its potential as an anti-onchocercal agent. Given the urgent need for macrofilaricidal agents with novel mechanisms of action, computationally guided screening of plant-derived compounds presents a cost-effective and time-efficient strategy for identifying lead molecules that target essential parasite enzymes [26,27]. The present study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by providing a preliminary in silico assessment of *A. muricata* phytochemicals as modulators of Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2. The findings could guide downstream biochemical validation, facilitate the design of dual-target therapeutics, and contribute to the development of integrated control strategies for onchocerciasis and potentially other filarial diseases [31].

Accordingly, we hypothesize that the diverse pharmacological profile of *A. muricata* could confer therapeutic potential against *O. volvulus* through the inhibition of Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2, enzymes essential for the parasite's survival and drug resistance. To investigate this, we employed molecular modeling approaches, ultimately identifying caffeic acid as a potential dual modulator of these target proteins.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Compound library identification, retrieval, and preparation

The phytochemicals present in *A. muricata* were identified and retrieved from the IMPPAT database in three-dimensional Structure Data Format (SDF) [33]. The retrieved compound structures were subsequently imported into Schrödinger's Maestro interface (Release 2024–1, Schrödinger, LLC, New York, NY, USA) and were subjected to preparatory protocols using LigPrep (OPLS3e force field, ionization

states generated at pH 7.0 ± 2.0 using Epik) as earlier reported by Onile et al. [21].

2.2. Target protein retrieval and preparation

The crystal structures of OV-GST1 (PDB ID: 2HNL) and OV-GST2 (PDB ID: 1TU7) [24] were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) [2]. Subsequently, the structures were prepared using the Protein Preparation Workflow of Schrödinger's Maestro, (Schrödinger Release 2024–1) with the OPLS3e force field, including the addition of hydrogens, assignment of bond orders, removal of crystallographic water molecules beyond 5 Å from the active site, and restrained energy minimization to converge heavy atoms to an RMSD of 0.3 Å [21].

2.3. Receptor grid generation and molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed using the Glide module (Schrödinger Release 2024–1) in Maestro. Receptor grids were generated for Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 using the Receptor Grid Generation tool. For Ov-GST1, the grid was centered on the co-crystallized ligand with coordinates $X = 17.11 \text{ \AA}$, $Y = 52.86 \text{ \AA}$, $Z = 27.84 \text{ \AA}$. For Ov-GST2, the grid center was set at $X = 17.57 \text{ \AA}$, $Y = -1.65 \text{ \AA}$, $Z = 24.36 \text{ \AA}$, also based on the co-crystallized ligand. The inner box, defining the volume explored by the ligand center during docking, was set to $10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ for both targets, while the outer box, which defines the volume used for grid potential calculations, was $24.07 \times 24.07 \times 24.07 \text{ \AA}$ for Ov-GST1 and $24.78 \times 24.78 \times 24.78 \text{ \AA}$ for Ov-GST2, with no additional constraints applied. These grids were subsequently used for docking the phytochemicals from *A. muricata* to predict binding modes and affinities using both the Standard precision (SP) and extra precision (XP) scoring functions of Glide.

2.4. Drug-likeness profiling and pharmacokinetics properties evaluation

The drug-likeness of the hit compounds obtained after molecular docking simulation was evaluated using the SwissADME webserver (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) based on Lipinski's rule of five [14]. Subsequently, the pharmacokinetic properties, including absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) parameters, were predicted using the pkCISM pharmacokinetics server (<http://biosig.unimelb.edu.au/pkcsim/>) [25]. All predictions were carried out using default server parameters and the SMILES of the compounds (Supplementary Table 1), and results were interpreted according to the thresholds described in the original references.

2.5. Binding free energy calculation

Following the molecular docking simulation, the Molecular Mechanics with Generalized Born and Surface Area (MM-GBSA) post-docking methodology of Maestro (Prime module, Schrödinger Release 2024–1) was employed to assess the stability of the hit compounds' interactions with the protein [20]. The Variable Solvent Generalized Born (VSGB) solvation model and the OPLS3 force field were employed, with other parameters kept default, and the hit compounds' binding free energies (G_{bind}) were calculated using the equations below [32]:

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta E + \Delta G_{\text{solv}} + \Delta G_{\text{SA}}$$

$$\text{energychange}(\Delta E) = E_{\text{complex}} - E_{\text{protein}} - E_{\text{ligand}}$$

where E_{complex} , E_{protein} , and E_{ligand} are the minimized energies of the protein-inhibitor complex, protein (E_{protein}), and inhibitor (E_{ligand}).

$$\Delta G_{\text{solv}} = G_{\text{solv}(\text{complex})} - G_{\text{solv}(\text{protein})} - G_{\text{solv}(\text{ligand})}$$

The solvation-free energy change (ΔG_{solv}) accounts for the difference

in solvation energies between the complex ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{complex})}$), protein ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{protein})}$), and inhibitor ($G_{\text{solv}(\text{ligand})}$).

$$\Delta\text{GSA} = G_{\text{SA}(\text{complex})} - G_{\text{SA}(\text{protein})} - G_{\text{SA}(\text{ligand})}$$

[15]. The surface area energy change (ΔGSA) reflects the difference in surface area energies between the complex (GSA (complex)), protein (GSA(protein)), and inhibitor (GSA(ligand)).

2.6. Molecular dynamics

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed for 100 ns for the best inhibitors against Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 using GROMACS software [29] with the OPLSA force field [1]. The topology of the ligands was generated using the SwissParam server (<http://www.swissparam.ch/>) [35], which supplies the necessary parameters for the simulation. The system was placed in a cubic simulation box, with all complexes solvated in TIP3P water molecules. To neutralize the overall charge of the system, Na^+ and Cl^- ions were added, replacing a portion of the water molecules to avoid steric clashes. This step ensured a charge-neutral system, which is crucial for accurate simulations [13]. The system was then minimized using the steepest descent method to eliminate any unfavorable steric contacts and relax the structure [3]. Following minimization, the system underwent equilibration. First, NVT equilibration was performed using the V-rescale thermostat [4] at 300 K for 1 ns to stabilize the temperature [11]. This was followed by NPT equilibration, using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat to maintain the system at constant pressure (1 atm) for another 1 ns, ensuring the correct thermodynamic conditions. Once the system reached equilibrium, a 100 ns production run was performed [12]. During this phase, the generated trajectories were analyzed to assess the stability and dynamic behavior of the ligand-receptor complexes.

3. Results

3.1. *A. muricata* compounds exhibited high affinities for OV-GST1 and 2

The 3D structures of the targets retrieved from the PDB were elucidated using the X-ray diffraction method and have a resolution of 1.50 Å and 2.00 Å, for OVGST 1 and 2, respectively. Notably, the structure of OVGST 1 possesses 225 amino acid residues while that of Ov-GST2 possesses 208 amino acid residues, respectively. The structures of the targets are depicted in Fig. 1.

The compounds retrieved from *A. muricata* were subjected to molecular docking against the target proteins to determine their binding affinities and interaction profiles with the respective proteins. As

evident in Table 1, IMPHY003421 exhibited the highest binding affinity for Ov-GST1 with a docking score of -7.764 kcal/mol, notably stronger than Ivermectin's score of -3.159 kcal/mol. Interestingly, IMPHY003421 also exhibited the highest binding affinity for OV-GST2, with a docking score at -10.021 kcal/mol, which is significantly lower than the other compounds and notably stronger than Ivermectin's -5.166 kcal/mol (Table 2). As evident in Table 2, eight *A. indica* compounds exhibited higher binding affinities for OV-GST2 compared to OV-GST1.

3.2. One *A. muricata* hit compound exhibited druglike properties

The potential of the hit compounds to serve as oral drug candidates was assessed based on the Ro5. As evident in Table 3, only IMPHY011933 (caffeic acid) was found to possess druglike properties, with IMPHY003241 (Galactomannan) having three violations. Interestingly, ivermectin was found to violate the Ro5.

3.3. ADMET profiling of druglike hit compounds

The ADMET profiling analysis, presented in Table 4, compares two druglike compounds, caffeic acid and Ivermectin, assessing their absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity to evaluate their potential as treatments for onchocerciasis. Ivermectin shows higher human intestinal absorption (87.6 %) than Caffeic Acid (69.407 %), suggesting better bioavailability. However, Caffeic Acid is more water-soluble, which may improve formulation ease. Both compounds

Table 1

The docking scores of the top ten compounds of OV-GST1 and the standard drug (Ivermectin).

Compound ID	Docking Score (kcal/mol)
IMPHY003421	-7.764
IMPHY011933	-7.045
IMPHY010081	-5.428
IMPHY011396	-3.696
IMPHY015016	-3.459
IMPHY014690	-3.274
IMPHY015838	-3.223
Ivermectin	-3.159
IMPHY017614	-2.908
IMPHY007041	-2.906
IMPHY006989	-2.796
IMPHY010097	-2.715
IMPHY007840	-2.524
IMPHY001505	-2.401

Fig. 1. The 3D X-ray crystallographic structure of OV-GST1 and 2. A) OV-GST1 and B) OV-GST2.

Table 2

The docking scores of the top ten compounds of OV-GST2 and the standard drug (Ivermectin).

Compound ID	Docking Scores (kcal/mol)
IMPHY003421	-10.021
Ivermectin	-5.166
IMPHY006362	-4.996
IMPHY011933	-4.53
IMPHY006700	-4.25
IMPHY012585	-4.153
IMPHY015838	-4.042
IMPHY007041	-3.964
IMPHY013971	-3.952
IMPHY010081	-3.873
IMPHY003478	-3.623
IMPHY006989	-3.34
IMPHY001223	-3.193
IMPHY0153483	-3.089
IMPHY015348	-3.089

have similar Caco-2 permeability, indicating comparable absorption potential.

Both compounds have limited blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, which reduces the risk of CNS-related side effects. Ivermectin shows lower BBB and central nervous system (CNS) permeability than Caffeic Acid, supporting its limited distribution to the brain. Caffeic Acid has a higher fraction unbound (0.529), suggesting more of it will be available in the bloodstream than Ivermectin (0.115).

Both compounds exhibit minimal interactions with CYP450 enzymes, except that Ivermectin is a substrate for CYP3A4. Both are non-substrates for the renal OCT2 transporter, suggesting minimal excretion via renal cation transport pathways.

Both compounds are non-toxic, as predicted by the Ames test, indicating a low potential for mutagenicity. Caffeic acid has a higher maximum tolerated dose (MTD) than Ivermectin, reflecting a wider safety margin. Ivermectin shows hepatotoxicity, while caffeic acid does not, which may make caffeic acid a safer option for long-term use. Both are non-inhibitors of hERG channels, implying low cardiotoxicity risk, and they are non-sensitizing to the skin. Oral acute toxicity (rat LD₅₀) predictions reported in mol/kg were converted to mg/kg using the equation below:

$$LD_{50}(\text{mg / kg}) = LD_{50}(\text{mol / kg}) \times \text{MolecularWeight}(\text{g / mol}) \times 1000$$

Caffeic acid and ivermectin exhibited predicted rat oral LD₅₀ values of 429,321 mg/kg and 2636,676 mg/kg, respectively, both exceeding the Class IV threshold. On extended classification scales, each is Class VI (low acute oral toxicity) [36].

3.4. Molecular interaction profiling

This shows the visualization and presentation of every interaction between the hit and standard compounds, and OV-GST1 and OV-GST2. The compounds formed hydrogen bonds with the amino acid residues constituting the active site of both proteins; in addition, there were also hydrophobic, positively and negatively charged, and polar interactions, as evident in Fig. 2.

Table 3

Drug-likeness properties of hit compounds from *A. muricata*.

Compound ID	Mol_MW ^a	donorHB ^b	acceptHB ^c	MLOGP ^d	Ro5 violation
Galactomannan (IMPHY003241)	504.44	11	16	-6.15	3
Caffeic acid (IMPHY011933)	180.16	3	4	0.7	0
Ivermectin	875.106	3	14	5.6	3

^a mol_MW is the molecular weight (range: < 500 Da).

^b donorHB is the number of hydrogen bond donors (range ≤ 5).

^c acceptHB is the number of hydrogen bond acceptors (range ≤ 10).

^d MLOGP is the octanol-water partition coefficient (range: -2.0-6.5).

3.5. Molecular dynamics simulation

3.5.1. Root mean square deviation (RMSD)

For the simulation of the promising ligands, caffeic acid and ivermectin, within the Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 proteins, the RMSD analyses of the complexes are depicted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively.

3.5.2. Root mean square fluctuation (RMSF)

The second parameter assessed using MD simulations is the RMSF of the protein, and the results are presented in Fig. 5.

3.5.3. Radius of gyration (Rg) and solvent accessible surface area (SASA)

To further evaluate the stability and behavior of our complexes, we calculated two key parameters: the Rg and SASA. The Rg results are presented in Fig. 6.

3.5.4. H-bond analysis

To analyze the interactions within our complexes, an H-bond analysis was conducted. The results are presented in Fig. 7.

Table 4

The ADMET Profiling of the Drug-like Hit Compounds.

Models	Compounds	
	Caffeic Acid	Ivermectin
Absorption		
HIA (% Absorbed)	69.407	87.6
Water solubility (mol/L)	-2.33	-4.668
Caco-2 permeability (log Papp in 10 ⁻⁶ cm/s)	0.634	0.637
P-gp (substrate)	Non-Substrate	Substrate
P-gp I (inhibitor)	Non-Inhibitor	Inhibitor
P-gp II (inhibitor)	Non-Inhibitor	Inhibitor
Distribution		
Blood-brain barrier (BBBW)	-0.647	-1.823
Central nervous system permeability (log PS)	-2.608	-3.129
Fraction unbound (Fu)	0.529	0.115
Metabolism		
CYP450 2C9 (inhibition)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
CYP450 2D6 (substrate)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
CYP450 2D6 (inhibition)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
CYP450 3A4 (substrate)	Non-Inhibitor	Inhibitor
CYP450 3A4 (inhibition)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
CYP450 1A2 (inhibition)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
CYP450 2C19 (inhibition)	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
Excretion		
Renal organic cation transporter 2 (OCT2)	Non-Substrate	Non-Substrate
Total Clearance	0.508	0.513
Toxicity		
AMES toxicity	Non-Toxic	Non-Toxic
Max tolerated dose (human)(mg/kg/day)	1.145	-1.454
hERG I inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
hERG II inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor	Non-Inhibitor
Oral Rat Acute Toxicity(mg/kg)	429,321 (Class VI)	2636,676 (Class VI)
Hepatotoxicity	Non-Toxic	Toxic
Skin Sensitization	Non-Toxic	Non-Toxic

Fig. 2. The 2D interactions of the hit compounds with the target proteins. **A:** Ov-GST1-Caffeic acid; **B:** Ov-GST1-Ivermectin; **C:** Ov-GST2-Caffeic acid; **D:** Ov-GST2-Ivermectin.

Fig. 3. RMSD analysis of protein and ligand stability in the Ov-GST1-Caffeic Acid and Ov-GST1-Ivermectin complexes.

Fig. 4. RMSD analysis of protein and ligand stability in the Ov-GST2-Caffeic Acid and Ov-GST2-Ivermectin complexes.

Fig. 5. RMSF analysis of protein flexibility in the studied complexes.

Fig. 6. RMSF analysis of protein flexibility in the studied complexes.

4. Discussion

River blindness, or onchocerciasis, is caused by the parasitic worm *O. volvulus*, which is spread by blackflies and affects millions of people globally, mostly in sub-Saharan Africa. The life cycle of the parasite and its extended stay in human tissues produce chronic inflammation, which can result in irreparable blindness and severe skin disorders [6]. The main medication now used to treat the illness is ivermectin; however, its drawbacks, including possible resistance and the inability to completely eradicate adult worms, highlight the necessity for alternate therapies and emphasize the need for alternative treatments [6,22]. Hence, this

study leveraged molecular modeling techniques to evaluate compounds from *A. muricata* as potential inhibitors of OV-GST1 and OV-GST2.

Following the molecular docking simulation, it was interesting to discover that some *A. muricata* compounds exhibited higher binding affinity for the target proteins compared to ivermectin. Notably, galactomannan exhibited the highest binding affinity among all the compounds, with docking scores of -7.764 kcal/mol and -10.021 kcal/mol for Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2, respectively, suggesting a strong and potentially stable interaction with the active sites of both proteins. Similarly, caffeic acid displayed high binding affinity for Ov-GST2, while its affinity for Ov-GST1 was comparable to that of ivermectin.

Fig. 7. Hydrogen bond interactions in the studied complexes.

These binding energies imply that both compounds can effectively occupy the active sites of the target enzymes, potentially inhibiting their catalytic activity, which is critical for parasite survival and drug resistance. Importantly, caffeic acid's favorable binding to both Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 underscores its potential as a dual-target inhibitor, enhancing its therapeutic promise against *O. volvulus*. Consequently, galactomannan and caffeic acid were designated as hit compounds and selected for downstream analyses. The observed differences in binding affinities also reflect the distinct structural features required to inhibit each protein effectively.

To further assess the potential of the hit compounds to serve as drugs, they were evaluated based on the Ro5. Notably, drug-likeness screening is a crucial step in the early stages of drug discovery and development. It involves evaluating the chemical and molecular properties of a compound to assess its potential to become a safe and effective drug. The goal of drug-likeness testing is to identify compounds that have a higher probability of success in subsequent stages of drug development, including efficacy, safety, and pharmacokinetics. Disappointingly, galactomannan, which exhibited the highest binding affinities for the proteins, was found to be non-druglike as it violated three parameters of the Ro5, including molecular weight and number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors. Conversely, caffeic acid satisfied the requirements for oral drug-likeness among the compounds examined. This is an essential indicator that the substance may be taken orally, which would be very beneficial for treating onchocerciasis in isolated locations. It was interesting for us to discover that ivermectin, which is an approved drug, violated three parameters of the Ro5.

A. muricata's caffeic acid and ivermectin differ in a few ways, according to the ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) profiling. In medication formulation, caffeine's increased water solubility and reduced intestinal absorption may be advantageous. Additionally, it exhibits a lesser propensity for toxicity, showing no symptoms of liver damage, a known side effect of ivermectin [5]. Caffeic acid's safety profile and capacity to prevent liver damage make it a desirable option for long-term therapy. A lower likelihood of drug interactions is also indicated by caffeine's little interaction with CYP enzymes, which can be advantageous for individuals who take many drugs at a time [7,8].

Caffeic acid binds stably to both Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 through a combination of hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic, π - π , polar, and charged interactions, consistent with its amphipathic scaffold comprising an aromatic ring, hydroxyls, and a carboxyl group. In Ov-GST1, the 3-hydroxyl group forms hydrogen bonds with ARG60 and HIS131, while the carboxylate oxygen forms hydrogen bonds with HIP74 and VAL75. The aromatic ring engages in π - π stacking with TYR32 and participates in hydrophobic contacts involving ARG38, PHE33, PHE123, ILE127, TRP63, and PHE225. Additional interactions include polar contacts with HIS131, positively charged interactions with ARG60 and ARG38, and a backbone interaction with GLY37. In Ov-GST2, the carboxylate group forms hydrogen bonds with HIP98 and TYR106, while hydrophobic contacts involve LEU13, ILE10, LEU50, TYR7, PHE8, and PHE38. Polar interactions are contributed by GLN49 and ASN203, and backbone interactions by GLY12 and GLY204, with the aromatic ring mediating additional hydrophobic contacts.

To further validate our molecular docking predictions, we compared the interaction profiles of caffeic acid with previously reported ligands targeting Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2. Notably, the residues engaged by caffeic acid largely overlap with those reported in the literature. Maraf et al. demonstrated that s-hexyl-GSH, a native ligand of Ov-GST2, forms hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic contacts with Tyr7, Phe8, Ile10, Leu13, Phe38, Gln49, Leu50, and Tyr106, directly corresponding to caffeic acid binding residues [16]. Similarly, Metuge et al. reported that plant-derived anti-Onchocerca compounds engage residues Leu50, Gln49, Ser63, and Arg95 in Ov-GST2 through hydrogen bonding, consistent with caffeic acid's interaction pattern [17]. For Ov-GST1, although fewer comparative data are available, prior studies highlight

the importance of hydrogen bonding and van der Waals interactions within the active site, mechanisms observed in caffeic acid docking. Collectively, these comparisons indicate that caffeic acid occupies the active sites of both Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 in a manner similar to previously validated ligands, forming interactions with residues critical for enzymatic activity, which supports the reliability of our in silico results.

For the simulation of the promising ligands, caffeic acid and ivermectin, within the Ov-GST1 protein, the RMSD analysis of the protein structure demonstrated that both complexes remained stable throughout the simulation, with minimal fluctuations. However, when examining the RMSD of the ligands, distinct differences in stability between the two complexes were observed. The Ov-GST1_ivermectin complex exhibited higher stability, as evidenced by a nearly linear RMSD plot over the course of 100 ns. The average RMSD value for ivermectin remained consistently below 1.7 nm, indicating strong and stable binding to the protein. In contrast, the Ov-GST1_caffeic acid complex displayed significant fluctuations during the initial 15 ns of the simulation. After this initial period of instability, the complex stabilized for the remainder of the simulation, achieving an average RMSD value of approximately 3 nm.

Similarly, these two ligands were evaluated for their inhibitory potential against Ov-GST2. The RMSD analysis of the protein structure revealed an initial increase in RMSD values for both complexes during the first 60 ns. After this period, the RMSD plots stabilized, with an average value of approximately 0.3 nm, indicating the structural stability of the protein in both cases. Regarding the RMSD analysis of the ligands, distinct behaviors were observed. For the Ov-GST2_ivermectin complex, significant destabilization occurred during the first 35 ns, with fluctuating RMSD values. However, following this phase of conformational adjustment, the ligand stabilized with an average RMSD of around 1 nm. Conversely, the Ov-GST2_caffeic acid complex showed minor fluctuations in RMSD values between 0.4 and 1 nm during the first 45 ns. After this period, the RMSD values increased significantly, reaching approximately 1.6 nm, before stabilizing for the remainder of the simulation.

The second parameter calculated using MD simulations is the RMSF of the protein. The results showed that the majority of residues in Ov-GST1, in both complexes, exhibited stable behavior with RMSF values not exceeding 0.2 nm. Only a few residues displayed slightly higher fluctuations, with RMSF values ranging between 0.2 and 0.26 nm. In contrast, the majority of residues in Ov-GST2 demonstrated fluctuations with RMSF values that did not exceed 0.3 nm. However, when comparing the residue movements between the two ligands, it was observed that the proteins bound to ivermectin exhibited greater stability compared to those bound to caffeic acid.

To better assess the stability and behavior of our complexes, we calculated two key parameters: Rg and SASA. Rg results demonstrated stable behavior for all four complexes, Ov-GST1_caffeic acid, Ov-GST1_ivermectin, Ov-GST2_caffeic acid, and Ov-GST2_ivermectin, with mean values of 1.76 ± 0.01 nm, 1.77 ± 0.01 nm, 1.72 ± 0.01 nm, and 1.70 ± 0.01 nm, respectively. These consistent values indicate that the overall compactness of the protein structures remained stable throughout the simulation. Similarly, SASA results revealed mean values of 117.74 ± 1.89 nm², 118.43 ± 1.63 nm², 112.09 ± 1.74 nm² and 111.47 ± 2.05 nm², respectively. These values reflect the exposure of the protein surface to the solvent, with minor differences observed between complexes. Overall, the Rg and SASA results confirm the stability of all complexes, with ivermectin contributing to slightly more compact structures and consistent solvent exposure compared to caffeic acid.

To analyze the interactions within our complexes, an H-bond analysis was conducted. The results indicate that all complexes were stabilized with an average of 1 H-bond over the 100 ns simulation, except for the Ov-GST1_Caffeic_Acid complex, which exhibited fewer stable interactions. The most stable complex was Ov-GST1_ivermectin, which consistently demonstrated 2 H-bonds throughout the simulation, highlighting its stronger and more stable interaction with the protein.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated *Annona muricata* phytochemicals as potential inhibitors of *O. volvulus* glutathione-S-transferases (Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2), key enzymes essential for parasite survival and persistence. Molecular docking identified galactomannan and caffeic acid as top candidates, with galactomannan showing the highest predicted binding affinity. However, drug-likeness assessment indicated multiple Ro5 violations for galactomannan, whereas caffeic acid met all drug-like criteria, supporting its suitability for oral administration. ADMET profiling further highlighted caffeic acid's favorable pharmacokinetic and safety attributes, including high water solubility, low toxicity risk, and minimal potential for drug–drug interactions relative to ivermectin. Molecular dynamics simulations demonstrated stable binding of caffeic acid within the active sites of both Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2, corroborated by RMSF, Rg, SASA, and hydrogen-bond analyses.

Collectively, these results position caffeic acid as a potential dual inhibitor of Ov-GST1 and Ov-GST2 with potential application as a macrofilaricidal agent. Beyond identifying a novel lead compound, this work demonstrates the utility of computational screening in accelerating anti-filarial drug discovery from medicinal plants. The findings could inform the design of dual-target therapeutics, guide experimental validation pipelines, and contribute to the development of integrated control strategies for onchocerciasis and other filarial diseases. Nevertheless, *in vitro* and *in vivo* investigations remain necessary to confirm its efficacy, safety, and therapeutic potential.

Funding

No funding was received for this research.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Taiwo Oluwakemi Adubi: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Miriam Chisom Amalu:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tolulope Adelonpe Onile:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Amal Bouribab:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Samir Chtita:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Samson Olugbenga Onile:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

Nil.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ins.2025.100085](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2025.100085).

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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